

NEEDS ANALYSIS IN ESP FOR MEDICAL STUDENT: A COURSE TO ENHANCE ACADEMIC PRESENTATION SKILLS

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Abstract: This paper presents the account of designing a course for first year students pursuing their studies in medical field. It elaborates on the detail procedure of developing ESP course for medical student. The paper provides a rationale to design the course, analyse the needs of specific learners, study the situation needed for academic presentation, and tailoring the authenticity-featured materials. The information in it can be resourceful to ESP teachers teaching medical students and also research scholars may conduct further research on the effectiveness of ESP course.

IndexTerms - ESP, EAP, Medical Students, Academic presentation skills.

I. INTRODUCTION

ESP is a course designed for a specific set of learners to enhance their communicative competence, which is relevant and applicable in specific professions. Such courses are designed based on the need analysis of learners and fulfil the learners' goal, focusing on language skills, discourse, genres that are appropriate in specific context and needs. John Munby (1978) states that "ESP courses are those where the syllabus and materials are determined in all essentials by the prior analysis of the communicative needs of the learner." It mainly emphasizes the needs of learners such as communicative needs, syllabus and materials. The learners' material and syllabus are prepared to meet the needs of the learners. It is because it is considered that the need for analysis has a vital role in the process of designing and carrying out any language course whether it is ESP or general English. It focuses on the specificity of the time, place, and people.

Robinson (1980) states that ESP can be used by a specific group of students, meant for a particular place and can be used only once. It focuses on the specific set of students, so it involves the need for analysis of that particular set of students and it helps the students to fulfil their goals. Since it is developed based on the needs of the particular set of students, it becomes less possible for other sets of students to use it. It adds burden to the teachers as they need more time and effort each time to prepare each material.

While Hutchinson and Waters (1987) define ESP as an approach to course design which starts with the question: 'why do these learners need to learn English?' What distinguishes ESP from General English is not the existence of a need as such but rather an awareness of the need. They focus on the awareness of the need and Strevens (1988) too agrees that ESP focuses on both the need of the learner and also the specificity of the discipline. Dudley-Evans and John (1998) define ESP as designed to meet the specific needs of the learners including skills, knowledge gaps. It is centred on the language (grammar, lexis, register), skills, discourse and genres appropriateness to these activities. It gives importance to the usage of underlying methodology and activities. ESP has been classified as EAP and EOP which includes further classification such as EVP, EMP, EBP, ELP, and ESCP.

Lorenzo (2005) reminds that ESP "concentrates more on language in context than on teaching grammar and language structures". Carter (1983) believes that ESP courses turns learners into users of the language. It is clear that the full features are directly related to ESP because students' requirements are very important when designing language activities. Robinson (1991), has classified ESP courses according to the professional area. A distinction is made between studying a language and discourse of various fields for academic purposes and professional purposes. The course intended to develop falls under EAP, as it is designed to cater the needs of students in their academics. The course developed will guide and help the students to do their academic presentation in a well organised manner. This may help them not only in their academics but also in their occupation (career as doctor).

II. CONTEXT AND RATIONALE

The course titled "A short-term course in Academic Presentation Skills for the first year MBBS students of "The Tamil Nadu Dr.M.G.R Medical University" aims to develop academic presentation skills in a medical context. The target group of learners (first year MBBS students), are newly transited from school and they are preparing to study medicine, practice medicine, and also be professionally fluent in the mentioned field. The academic environment in school and in medical college differs in terms of teaching-learning methodology, the mode of assessment, and other academic activities. Therefore, acquiring knowledge about academic presentation skills will help them in their academics as well as in their career as a doctor.

Effective oral case presentations help facilitate information transfer among physicians and are essential to delivering quality patient care. Oral case presentations are also a key component of how medical students and residents are assessed during their training. At its core, an oral case presentation functions as an argument. It is the presenter's job to share the pertinent facts of a patient's case with the other members of the medical care team and establish a clear diagnosis and treatment plan. Moreover, as medical students, they have to do case studies, write reports, present papers at conferences, take seminars, and do self-directed teaching. Later as junior doctors they are expected to present new cases to their consultants in daily ward rounds, and clinics. Moreover, if these students want to go for higher studies and also in their career, they need to present papers, attend conferences and write and publish journals, and other related avenues. Thus, it is useful for students to learn academic presentation skills to excel in the medical profession. This course aims to equip students with the skills which would help in academic as well as occupational contexts.

III. NEEDS ANALYSIS

Needs analysis is the mechanism of introducing the 'what' and 'how' of a course. It is the elementary point in the course design process in which different data will be gathered to help the practitioner to decide about the focus of the course, content in terms of language, skills and methodology. It is recognized as the foundation of English for Specific Purposes (ESP). In the initial stages of ESP (the 1960s and early 1970s), needs analysis incorporated assessing the communicative needs of the learners and the techniques of executing limited teaching objectives. Presently, the function of needs analysis is much more intricate: it intends to accumulate information about the learners and define the target situation and environment of studying ESP. Hutchinson and Waters (1987) define needs analysis based on the difference between ESP and General English (GE). "What distinguishes ESP from GE is not the existence of a need as such but rather an awareness of the need" (P.53). Thus, the awareness of the need of English influences the development of relevant content in the language course. It is said that the process of needs analysis often entails collecting information for the sake of having the necessary foundation to develop a course to meet the needs of a particular group of students.

In this regard, Richards and Platt (1992) state that Need Analysis is "the process of determining the needs for which a learner or a group of learners acquires a language and arranges the needs according to priorities." Graves (2000) notes that it is a systematic and ongoing process of gathering information about student's needs and interpreting the information in order to have an effective course to meet the needs. It is also a "procedure used to collect information about learners' needs" Richards (2001,p.51). Therefore, it is mandatory for an ESP teacher to be occupied in the process to collect information about "what" the learner needs and "how" he can learn. The above definitions indicate the existence of different types of needs that the ESP course teacher should take into consideration while designing a course.

According to Hutchinson and Waters (1987), target needs are mainly related to what the learner needs to do in the target situation. ESP practitioners should gather information about learners' necessities, lacks, and wants. The need for language items, skills, strategies, and subject knowledge should be studied to design the course effectively. Necessities are the requirements of the target situation. It could be occupational or academic requirements. It gives information on what the learner has to know in order to function effectively in the target situation. Accordingly, needs "are perhaps more appropriately described as objectives" (Robinson, 1991, P.) to be achieved.

Lacks are the gaps between the initial or actual situation of the learners in terms of language proficiency or aptitudes, and the one which is required after the accomplishment of the language training. Wants are learners' personal expectations and hopes towards acquiring English in their language course. It is subjective because it is a very personal expectation. In this respect, an individual's wants cannot all be accounted for; however, the wants of the majority can be discussed and partially met.

Target situation analysis guides the way to the destination of the course. It is the learner needs to influence the route between the starting point (lacks) and the destination (necessities). The concept of "learning needs" by Hutchinson & Waters and their analysis of it have been proven to be fairly useful in practice because it clarifies the means through which learners proceed to achieve their target needs starting with realization of shortcomings. Course designers need to analyse the learner's learning needs. According to their motivation, the conditions of the learning situation, and their existing knowledge and skills the target situation analysis can give information on what people do with language while analysis on learning needs can state how people learn to do what they do with language.

IV. NEEDS ANALYSIS FOR THE COURSE DESIGN

Needs analysis or needs assessment is an integral part of language curriculum development. It lays the foundation for lesson planning, syllabus design, materials evaluation and development, and instructional design and assessment development. Thus, it is one of the critical parts of ESP course planning and designing. It will be impossible to produce the relevant material if it fails to gather the needs of teachers, students, parents, and administrators. (West, 1994, as cited in Flowerdew, 2013b, p. 326). Belcher (2006, p. 135) points out that "needs assessment is seen in ESP as the foundation on which all other decisions are, or should be, made".

Need analysis helps to gather information in designing a relevant course that would influence the learners' education as well as in their future profession. To decide the sources of information means to ask the question "Who should decide what the language needs are?" (West, 1994: p. 6). Therefore, the main sources for needs analysis are learner, teacher, and company. West (1994) frames it as a triangle framework: teacher-perceived, student-perceived and company-perceived needs. While Long (2005) adds to the list such as triangulated sources and literature. West (1994) also names other possible sources, such as former students, those already working in the target situation and specialist informants. Hutchinson and Waters (1987, p.60) recommends seeking information from a variety of sources and attempting 'a satisfactory compromise'. Similarly, Long (2005) too confirms that "multiple sources should always be employed, both because they add breadth and depth to an analysis (p.63).

For this course, learners were a key source of information for need analysis. Through their perception, the first pillar of ESP approach can be understood. This was followed by professionals belonging to medical science to understand the gap between their knowledge of language and what they require and also collected information regarding the current practices related to English courses in the chosen university. Documents or literature available on related fields were also one source to gather comprehensive information related to existing courses and its challenges or recommendations.

V. METHODOLOGY

The main purpose of needs analysis is to develop a course that will be relevant for learners and in the case of English for Specific Purposes, the needs analysis is mainly to gather information on Target Situation Analysis (TSA), Learner Situation Analysis (LSA), and Present Situation Analysis (PSA). In other words, it helps to understand the learner's or participant's needs, motivations, and behaviors. Some of the common tools used for needs analysis are surveys/questionnaires, interviews, participant observation, non-participant observation, Triangulated method, review of relevant literature, report studies.

For this course, the survey was the main tool to gather the needs of our learners. To gather data on Learners' needs and target situation, a questionnaire was framed. The questionnaire consists of close-ended and open-ended questions covering TSA, LSA, PSA questions. To avoid ambiguous responses Likert scale, paired comparisons, checklists were implemented in questionnaires. While understanding the participants' expectations from the ESP course, we have incorporated open-ended questions.

Before framing the questionnaire, the team had an informal interview with the target population. This was mainly to get background information on the project- such as establishing the sustainability of the course we develop. Apart from that it is to construct relevant and suitable questions in survey forms (questionnaire) and pave the way for needs assessment and evaluation to other tools such as structured interviews and triangulation study.

Further a review of relevant literature were made and included authentic materials. This was mainly to understand the learner's need, in this case it was mainly to get information on types of the presentation done in the medical profession, and medical content used for presentation. Later, these literature reviews formed a foundation to develop classroom material for the course.

The intended target population for the course 'Academic Presentation skills' is the first year MBBS student. The project team contacted a Plastic surgeon and medical students and had a discussion on explaining the need of English course. After a deep analysis, it was concluded that course on Academic presentation needs to be developed. The information was a good resource since they provided with background information about the institution and the learners helped us decide the tools for conducting the needs analysis. Since learners' needs to play a crucial role in developing the course, contacting the students who are studying in the target university paved the way for us in conducting the needs analysis.

After gathering background information about the target population, the project team decided that a survey should be the main tool to gather data on the learners' needs and target situation. Authentic materials were also used as one of the tools for the needs analysis. To understand the situation of the learners and the focus of the course, various relevant literature were reviewed which helped in understanding various types of presentation practiced in the medical field and medical contents which are important for presentation.

Understanding learners' needs, target situation, and present situation, a survey questionnaire was framed using google form. The questionnaire includes closed and open-ended questions which would help us understand the needs of the learners without ambiguity. The questionnaire consists of 36 questions with a choice of answers and statements with which the respondents could state if they agree or disagree. The senior students whom we contacted helped us circulate the google form to the learners and we received responses. The information gathered through this survey made us understand the learners' lack, wants, needs and their expectation from the course.

VI. DATA ANALYSIS

Thirteen medical students from the Tamil Nadu Dr.M.G.R Medical University participated in the needs analysis process. All the participants are doing their First Year of MBBS and are aged between 20 to 22. All the participants are Indian citizens and Tamil is their first language except for one which is Malayalam. The 13 participants had practiced English as their medium of instruction in the 12th standard and in junior college.

All the data we collected through the questionnaire are analyzed as follows.

Figure 1

The graph above shows that 53.8% of the participants studied in an English medium school, while 46.2% did not have English as a medium of instruction in their junior college.

Which of the following activities do you frequently do in your classroom? Choose any number of options. *
13 responses

Figure 2

The above Figure 2 indicates that the respondents frequently had to do presentations as a classroom task as well as for their assessment. Presentation on specific topics was mostly practiced which accounts for 61.5% followed by seminar presentations (53.8%) and oral case presentations with 46.2%.

Tick the purposes for which you usually make academic presentation in classroom. (You can choose more than one).

13 responses

Figure 3

The bar graph in figure 3 represents the purpose of doing academic presentations for target learners. 76.9% of the population said that it is part of assessment, 61.5% said it is 'part of classroom task'. 23.1% said that is mandatory in the curriculum and 5.4% said they need it as preparation for future needs, and other purposes for academic presentations.

The table represents the Present Situation Analysis of respondents. The questionnaire shared fourteen problem statements and used Likert scale to enable respondents to select the best suited option.

Table 6.1:

S.No	Problems	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	While making presentations, I have problem because I fear facing audience	7.7%	15.4%	30.8%	38.5%	7.7%
2	While making presentations, I have problems because I am not confident in speaking English.	30.8%	23.1%	-	46.2%	-
3	While making presentations, I have problem because I am not aware of how to make presentation	23.1%	30.8%	15.4%	30.8%	-
4	While making presentations, I have problems because I lack content knowledge.	30.8%	23.1%	15.4%	23.1%	7.7%
5	I have a problem because I have never done presentations before and so I feel nervous.	23.1%	15.4%	23.1%	38.5%	-
6	I have trouble making a coherent presentation using appropriate linkers and discourse markers.	23.1%	15.4%	38.5%	23.1%	-
7	I have trouble preparing effective power point presentation slides using visuals.	30.8%	23.1%	23.1%	23.1%	-
8	I have trouble in grabbing the attention of the audience through effective introductions.	30.8%	23.1%	23.1%	15.4%	7.7%
9	I have trouble developing academic arguments, presenting evidence, citation using appropriate context specific vocabulary.	23.1%	-	61.5%	15.4%	-
10	I have trouble speaking without the written script. Or I read what I have to say.	30.8%	7.7%	38.5%	23.1%	-

11	I have trouble understanding and responding to audience questions.	23.1%	53.8%	23.1%	-	-
12	I have difficulty with pronunciation of medical terms.	30.8%	30.8%	23.1%	7.7%	7.7%
13	I have difficulty in using appropriate intonation for effective communication.	15.4%	38.5%	23.1%	23.1%	-
14	I have fluency issues.	15.4%	38.5%	7.7%	38.5%	-

Through the analysis, it is found that most of the respondents agreed that they face issues in making academic presentation due to following reasons:

- Not confident in speaking English (46.2%)
- Fluency issues (38.5%)
- Fear of facing audience (38.5%)
- Nervous as they do not have experience in it (38.5%)
- Not aware of how to make presentation (30.8%)

I have trouble developing academic arguments, presenting evidence, citation using appropriate context specific vocabulary.
13 responses

Figure 4

However, the question on developing academic arguments, presenting evidence, citation using appropriate context specific vocabulary had a neutral response from the respondents with 61.5 %.

Would you like a course in Academic presentation skills? Yes/No Which of the following would you like to learn in the course? (You can choose more than one option) *
13 responses

Figure 5

Analysis shown in figure 5 provides an insight into the Target Situation Analysis. It indicates target learners' need of academic presentation, content areas to focus on and also as a course developer it provides input to develop relevant EAP for medical students in 'The Tamil Nadu Dr.M.G.R Medical University.

It is determined from figure 5 that the majority of the participants opted to learn to speak fluently using appropriate academic vocabulary-and without pauses, hesitations and fillers, followed by 38.5% of respondents who aspire to learn to design effective power-point presentation slides using visual and graphs. Respondents also opted to learn to use interactive strategies and learn to use various ICT tools to make presentation slides.

The graph below shows the respondents' preference for different classroom activities.

Figure 6

From the data presented in figure 6, it is evident that the respondents prefer to practice academic presentation. Along with that, preference for analysing presentations using criteria/templates, and practice making presentation slides were opted for, while watching recorded presentations on topics related to medicine was least preferred.

State your preference for classroom task/activities.
13 responses

Figure 7

For classroom activities, almost half of the respondents preferred to work in combination of individual, pair, and group work. Another option is to provide individual and pair work or individual and group work. It indicates that respondents prefer to have individual classroom activities for this course with a combination of either pair or group work.

Figure 8

With reference to figure 9, 61.5% of the respondents would like their teacher to show videos of academic talk from various medical disciplines which would help or guide them in their course. While other options had constant response and did not have other options stated.

Figure 9

For the question on the feedback system in figure 10, most of the respondents want their teacher to correct their mistakes personally, followed by recording their presentation and discussing with the tutor personally. Peer correction was the least chosen option.

Question 33 to 36 aimed to study learner needs and learner's preference on taking this course. It also tried to elicit when they would like the course to be conducted and their expectation from the course.

Figure 10

According to figure 11, it is indicated that 84.6% of the respondents want the course on Academic Presentation to be held simultaneously with their core course while 15.4% choose to have it during their semester break. Those who choose to have it simultaneously with their core course, preferred to have one hour a day for four weeks.

As represented in figure 12 below, 53.8% of the respondents choose one hour a day for 4 weeks while 23.1% choose to have it two hours every Saturday for 10 weeks.

Figure 11

The pie chart in figure 13 shows that 69.2% of the respondents prefer to have classes in the morning while 30.8% have opted for evening class.

Which session do you prefer to have a class?
13 responses

Figure 12

Respondents were asked to write down their expectations from course and the answers given were as follows:

- To give us the guidelines and show us an example on how to present, make us practice and point out and correct our mistakes.
- I expect to be more confident in front of others.
- To build up confidence and make my point clear to the audience.
- More effective use of technology for academic presentations.
- To speak in English confidently and fluently.
- To fill the gap of my English knowledge via your input and guidance.

VII. FINDINGS

From the Data Analysis, it is observed that

- Respondents have expressed the need for Academic presentation because it is a part of their assessment and classroom task.
- Participants find challenges in facing the audience and often feel nervous. They are not confident speaking in English as they could not use the language fluently. They also lack knowledge in using visual aids for their presentation slides.
- The respondents prefer to learn to design effective power point presentation slides using visuals, graphics and speak fluently using appropriate academic vocabulary - without pauses, hesitations, excessive fillers.
- Most of the participants want to practice academic presentations and analyse them using criteria and templates with the tutor and they opted to do their activities individually, in pairs or as a group.
- They expect the teacher to show videos of academic talk from various medical disciplines and correct their mistakes by calling them out and correct it personally.
- They prefer to do their academic presentation course simultaneously with their core course having one hour a day for four weeks in the morning.

VIII. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE COURSE

Aims are the general statements that are set to be achieved at the end of the course. They are the long-term goals and provide a direction to the course. It is a concise description of the overall goals or purposes of a program, a module, or an individual lecture. They are like 'mission statements' that summarise the scope and value of the course (Education Development Unit, 2021). While Learning objectives are brief descriptions of how aims can be fulfilled. It explains the operational aspects of teaching-learning in more detail than the aims. Therefore, objectives are specific statements. They are the short-term goals that could be achieved within the scope of the course itself. It describe exactly what the student should be able to do and help achieve the aims of the course.

In an ESP Course, the overall goals could be based on the learners' needs as well as the institution's vision. The learning objectives of ESP focused on ways that are directly linked with the results of a needs analysis. To have effective learning objectives, it is necessary to know target learners thoroughly and analyse the learners' target language context, identify specific skills and sub-skills that members of the discourse community use.

Therefore, the course aims to develop academic presentation skills. Target learners will learn presentation techniques such as (a) how to plan, structure, organize academic presentations, (b) develop ideas coherently using appropriate discourse markers, and (c) use appropriate academic language (vocabulary and structures) and presentation strategies to deliver effective presentations.

After the completion of the course, students will be able to:

1. Gather information and ideas on specific topics, structure and organize them logically, using advanced organizers and concept maps.
2. Develop the ideas using supporting details such as comparing, giving reasons, contrasting, giving examples, etc.
3. Introduce the topic and objectives clearly by giving an overview of the presentation
4. Prepare slides highlighting information through visual aids like diagrams, charts, etc
5. Use formal academic language (topic-specific terms and structures) to present the arguments, with citations and references.
6. Use interactive strategies like asking questions to the audience to keep them involved.

IX. SYLLABUS

A syllabus is a document containing information on topics or content to be covered in a course of study. Richards et al. (1996) define a syllabus as a description of the contents of a course of instruction and the order in which they are to be taught. A syllabus is a composed set of prospects for a course. It generally contains course policies, comprehensive content items, rules and regulations, required and optional texts, and assessment procedures. It assists learners to stay responsible for their learning. This document also carries learning goals and is generally distributed at the beginning of the course. The syllabus also specifies course objectives and the necessary materials. It also acts as a pledge among a faculty department and its students.

The course that we intend to develop is particularly for students pursuing their studies in medicine. It is an EAP course that focuses on improving academic presentation skills. Its main purpose is to familiarise students with basic skills of academic presentation which will help them not only in academics but also in their Profession. To excel in the academic presentation, the learner needs to identify good practices for academic presentation, control the tone of voice to have an impactful presentation, and use the visual aids effectively. All these factors would be covered in the course. Niazi (2012) as cited in Lodhi, Shamim, Robab, Shahzad, & Ashraf (2018) asserted that Medical English language teaching is a new and modern approach, and it should be different from the teaching of the general English language. Medical students possess medical knowledge and skills in their medical education, this ESP course should enable participants to use the English language in their medical studies rather than learning grammar and other structures. DuGas, Esson, Ronaldson (1999) suggest a lesson format for such courses where a syllabus follows Lesson A and B. Lesson A establishes its centre on vocabulary presentation and acquisition, the lesson B gives a chance to apply learning from the preceding lesson into context.

Similarly, the ESP course intends to form an integrated syllabus. It is because an integrated syllabus connects different areas of study by cutting across subject-matter lines and emphasizing unifying concepts. Integration focuses on making connections for students, allowing them to engage in relevant, meaningful activities that can be connected to real life. This course aims to improve medical student's academic presentation skills which should be an integration of presentation skills in context to the medical field or scenario. Thus, the syllabus will be an integration of learner-centered syllabus, Content-based syllabus, and Task-based syllabus.

Learner-centered syllabus relies on learners knowing what they need to do in English and what they need to learn to develop the skills they need. The syllabus includes concepts that would enrich the skills of the learner which in our case focuses on the academic presentation skills. The course would cover topics and skills that are related and needed for an impactful presentation that is specific to the learner's needs. A content-based syllabus is a language teaching syllabus that integrates subject and linguistic matter where teachers focus on content or language aspect with minimal effort to teach language separately. The participants of the course are medical professionals who have medical knowledge and have a purpose to pursue this course. Therefore, this type of syllabus will motivate them to learn as they will feel the progress from what they know, what needs to be learned, and what is provided to them.

Furthermore, the task-based syllabus focuses on using tasks to help learners deploy language communicatively as the tasks represent real-world language. Lodhi et al., (2018) suggest that a course should be designed for the health department with the concept of how to improve learners' learning in an ESL context. The skill-based syllabus is also relevant to the course as they focus on language abilities. The medical students need to be taught how to deliver their speech or presentation effectively and for this, the learner needs the skills of reading and academic writing which fall within the purview of a skill-based syllabus.

X. MATERIALS

Material writing for ESP is one of the distinct characteristics as compared to General English. The teaching and learning process is a complex and dynamic process with all the various factors influencing each other. Furthermore, the success of ESP courses is determined by the classroom materials and methods that are chosen to operationalize these objectives. According to Anthony (2018), materials and methods stand as the third pillar of the ESP approach. In ESP settings, the teaching materials are usually not readily available. Thus, classroom materials are decided at the administrative level by ESP course and program designers. These might be adopted or adapted from existing sources, such as published textbooks, or they may be newly created based on authentic materials from the target setting.

These are referred to as in-house materials, tailor-made materials, locally produced materials, self-designed materials, internal materials, home-made materials, or home-grown materials. In ESP, course designers have the freedom to adopt, adapt, or create materials for their specific learners and usually do not commit to a single learning theory or teaching methodology. Therefore, need analysis can help establish what to teach, and select teaching methodologies to meet the needs of learners.

Figure 13

Hutchinson and Waters (1987) state that " Good materials do not teach: they encourage learners to learn" (p. 107). They provide a principle that can guide material development. It is listed as below:

- Materials should provide a stimulus to learning. It should include interesting texts, enjoyable activities which enable learners to engage in thinking capacities, and opportunities for learners to use existing knowledge and skills.
- The material should have a clear and coherent unit structure. This will help teachers in planning lessons and encourage learners with a sense of progress and achievement. It should also be clear and systematic but flexible enough to allow for creativity and variety.
- Materials should include the nature of language and learning. While writing materials, developers should consider the learner's learning process and incorporate diverse activities.
- Materials should reflect the nature of the learning task. It should create a balanced outlook reflecting the complexity of the task and making it manageable.
- Materials can be useful when introduced with new techniques.
- Materials should provide models of correct and appropriate language use. '... materials become simply a statement of language use rather than a vehicle for language learning' (Hutchinson and Waters, 1987).

Figure 14

The diagram above represents the ESP material design model. Task is the primary focus that acts as a vehicle in carrying language and content for their language development for specific purposes. The language and content are drawn from input and one selected according to what learners will need in order to do the task.

In this course, various kinds of authentic materials will be used since it will help students realise the real-world scenario and make the learning more engaging and relevant. Further, it will motivate them since they will get an opportunity to apply their knowledge with English language. We will be using Youtube videos, magazine articles, picture strips and other medical resources. These materials are selected with an intent to allow students to learn and practice Academic Presentation Skills with medical contents.

XI. CONCLUSION

The project on developing a short-term course in Academic presentation skills is intended to offer to first year MBBS students of The Tamil Nadu Dr.M.G.R Medical University. The idea was generated from one of the members uncle who is a doctor in profession and shared about the challenges medical professionals face in using English language during their presentation. The course can be categorized as English for (Academic) Medical Purposes as it aims to enhance participants' academic presentation skills specifically in the medical field. The need analysis illustrated that the majority of the target learners did not have much of an experience and lacked confidence to present. Therefore, the syllabus was developed in a way that learners get ample practice sessions. Since the course demands learners to integrate their medical knowledge and use of English language, the syllabus followed is integrated syllabus. To motivate learners and create a sense of purposeful learning authentic materials were used. As a

course developer the project helped us in gaining enormous insights on presentation skills and differences between academic presentation and presentation skills. It was an opportunity to learn and gain effective presentation skills.

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